

Robot Behaviours for Transparent Human-Robot Interaction

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Abstract—The absence of transparency in robot processes presents a substantial obstacle to facilitating effective human-robot collaboration, particularly in response to the escalating need for autonomous human-robot interaction. This challenge assumes greater significance in non-industrial contexts, as it hinders humans from understanding a robot’s intentions, progress, and decision-making rationale, critical elements for fostering smooth interactions. To address this critical issue, this research introduces two distinct methodologies for integrating transparent behaviours into social robots: a by-design and a by-learning approach. Our preliminary results showed that incorporating non-verbal cues significantly enhanced the robot’s transparency, leading to a more engaging interaction for human participants.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of robots into various human-centred environments is steadily increasing, particularly in non-industrial contexts. In such settings, where Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) is commonplace, it is crucial to carefully design robots’ behavioural patterns to ensure transparency. This transparency is essential for facilitating effective, seamless, and safe interactions between humans and robots. Transparent robot behaviours are not merely an enhancement but a fundamental requirement for fostering mutual understanding and harmonious coexistence between humans and robots.

The definition of transparency varies in the HRI literature, and there is no common agreement. Some authors identify transparency in the sense of predictability. For example, in [1] stated that “Transparency is essentially the opposite of unpredictability”. Other definitions associate the term with legibility. Wortham et al. [2] defined transparency as “Transparency is the term used to describe the extent to which the robot’s ability, intent, and situational constraints are understood by users”.

This paper, however, is in pair with [3] which includes all the aforementioned definitions. In our work, we define transparency as the fusion of legibility, explainability, and predictability, bearing in mind the definitions of Dragan et al. [4]. They explained that legibility enables observers to infer an agent’s objectives quickly, and predictability refers

to matching what an observer expects. Accordingly, transparency can be achieved by the combination of 3 properties:

- What the robot is doing (legibility).
- Why the robot is doing that (explainability).
- What the robot will do next (predictability).

Taking into account the above properties, it is vital to examine how to achieve transparency since, as indicated previously, a robot must transparently communicate its intended actions to reduce uncertainty. In [5], the authors noted that a stereotypical motion (a movement reproduced in a standardized form) could be legible and predictable. Additionally, [6] explained that using the robot’s complementary motions (e.g., gaze, hand gesture) could achieve legibility and make the motion more expressive. Consequently, forms of natural non-verbal communication are the key to achieving this behaviour. A first step, therefore, has been to study human behaviours because humans can naturally infer others’ behaviours by observing non-verbal cues. The present work proposes methods and explores mechanisms to create transparent robots’ behaviours during HRI scenarios.

II. PROPOSED APPROACH

Many existing approaches within the realm of HRI necessitate prior user training, often resulting in a deficiency of natural, efficient, and transparent robot behaviours, while a universal design approach in HRI literature for achieving transparency is neglected. This paper introduces two novel methodologies for establishing transparent robot behaviours in the context of social interaction. The first approach involves the development of inherently transparent robot behaviours, where effective non-verbal cues and actions are seamlessly integrated into the robot’s design. This approach aims to minimize the requirement for extensive user training, thus facilitating a more intuitive and user-friendly interaction experience. Drawing inspiration from studies employing Reinforcement Learning methods (e.g., [7]), our second proposed method creates transparent robot behaviour either through human intervention, by introducing preferred constraints during the robot’s learning process, or by learning human preferences to personalize and render the behavior transparent.

A. Transparent behaviour by-design

Human interaction is characterized by various complex communication strategies, often appearing unintentional, subconscious, and automatic. These non-verbal communication methods include gestures such as pointing or drawing attention to specific environmental entities and emotional expressions communicating internal states to others. For

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Fig. 1: Interactive Reinforcement Learning diagram.

instance, pointing is a ubiquitous human referential gesture employed to share an interest in an object or to accomplish a more distinct goal, such as retrieving the object [8].

Another essential category of non-verbal cues is communicative-intent-indicating behaviour [9], where individuals look at the observer’s face and eyes or make gestures in response to the observer’s attentional status. This behaviour indicates the person’s intention to influence another’s attention directly, signalling the sender’s desire for interaction and face-to-face attention.

Incorporating these non-verbal communication strategies into robotic systems could provide a more enriched communication channel than systems relying solely on text or speech-based interactions. These mechanisms, often informed by domain experts like psychologists, can enhance a robot’s transparency, reduce the necessity for user training, and explain the robot’s behaviours more intuitively. By making the robot’s state more transparent and thus more predictable, these non-verbal cues can facilitate greater understanding and predictability for the user.

However, it is crucial to note that humans hold strong expectations regarding aligning specific non-verbal cues with certain internal states [10]. Therefore, the robot’s non-verbal cues and the corresponding internal states should conform to naturally occurring human signals. Without careful design, a robot’s behaviour could potentially be perceived as confusing or misleading. Limitations in physical embodiment may prevent some natural signals from being applied to non-humanoid robots. Consequently, alternative signal modalities (e.g., light) should be employed to enhance their transparency and facilitate diverse levels of interaction.

B. Transparent behaviour by learning

Developing robots with social autonomy remains a complex task. The approach of embedding pre-determined, psychologist-informed behaviours into humanoid robots may not offer the most effective solution to the issue of their social acceptability. As the complexity of a robot’s internal state escalates, it becomes increasingly unmanageable for a designer to preemptively establish the entire range of cues the robot might need to exploit. As such, a more efficient approach we propose involves mechanisms such as Interactive Reinforcement Learning (IntRL) to generate personalized and transparent robot behaviour. IntRL allows a robot to learn from two distinct sources. The first source pertains to rewards gleaned from environmental observations, while the second corresponds to guidance or feedback from an auxiliary critic

source, such as human mentors, as illustrated in Figure 1. This dynamic model allows mentors to actively influence the robot’s actions by providing corrections or recommending constraints to the learning algorithm, thereby enhancing the transparency of the robot’s behaviour. While presenting significant advantages, more investigation is needed since IntRL has not yet been extensively applied as a meaningful learning method for robots to acquire transparent behaviour.

III. PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Preliminary findings ([11], [12], [13]) underscore the key role of transparent by-design cues in enhancing the efficacy of social robots during collaborative interactions with humans in navigation and learning scenarios.

Our current research is focused on investigating the proposed by-learning approach as a personalized, transparent creation of a robot’s behaviours. Future research should also explore the synergistic effects of different combinations of by-design cues.

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